

Challenges to Patriarchy: The Women Pioneers of Odisha

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ABSTRACT

The progress of any society depends on the indispensable contributions of women, which include their skills, enthusiasm, and cooperation. But, throughout history, women have faced oppression at the hands of men who enforced various societal norms that were unjust and restrictive. The phenomenon of women being objectified for enjoyment and practising superstitions, traditions, and cultural customs to restrict them has occurred gradually over time. The societal perception of women as objects rather than subjects is influenced by a patriarchal attitude. The degree of social progress in a society is intricately connected to the extent of gender equality in terms of healthcare, education, work, and leisure possibilities for women. Nevertheless, in Odisha, women's equal status in society has been greatly damaged by societal problems such as restricted educational opportunities, child marriage, the practice of dowry, and girl-child infanticide. Throughout history, numerous women in Odisha have demonstrated courage by speaking out against patriarchal systems. They defied all obstacles and actively promoted women's rights. This paper examines the contributions made by famous women who, through their writing, fought against patriarchal norms. They pushed for gender equality, and women's participation in socio-economic, political, and religious arenas, and their writing contained strong expressions of defiance to patriarchal customs.

Keywords: Gender equality, Literature, Patriarchy, Women Pioneers.

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Introduction

Women in Odisha have been subjected to subordination since ancient times, and this subordination was seen in a variety of contexts. Women are not permitted to pursue higher education. Women were disadvantaged in the socio-economic sphere as a result of practices such as child marriage, Parada Pratha, girl child infanticide, the dowry system, and the prohibition on widow remarriage. On the other hand, a great number of women used their writing to fight against these blind practices. In Medieval times, a number of authors, such as Brundavati Devi, Tribhuvan Devi, and Nishanka Devi, dedicated themselves to the craft of writing within the realm of Odia literature. It is reasonable to consider them to be the first women authors of Odisha. During that period, an exclusive interest in religious and spiritual literary works was displayed by those who were literate and those who adhered to them. In the modern age, literary works were developed within the context of the political atmosphere that prevailed at the time and the difficulties that women were experiencing. Through their work, they posed a challenge to the patriarchy that was prevalent during that time.

Ancient Age

Women in ancient India occupied a position of great esteem and were greatly revered. Individuals engaged in outdoor activities based on the specific circumstances and situations they encountered, without any strict gender-based restrictions on designated roles for men.ⁱ Women had access to all the top educational opportunities. In this particular era, it is noteworthy to mention that certain women demonstrated exceptional education prowess. Their hymns, deemed of great value, have been incorporated into the esteemed Vedas. The term ‘Bramhavadinis’ refers to the women who can pursue and advance these studies. Several notable women emerged during that period, including Lopamudra, Apala, Kadru, Ghosa, Poularni, and Visvavara. Gargi was a philosopher who gained significant recognition during that period.ⁱⁱ The political instability and acts of terror that ensued from these attacks significantly impacted women, leading them to adopt the practice of *Purdaha* (The cultural practice of segregating women from men or strangers, mainly through a curtain, which is observed in particular Hindu societies). This practice hindered their intellectual development.

Medieval Age

The period is characterised by a significant development in literature, which can be attributed to the emergence of a new group of poets known as the Vaishnava poets of Odisha.ⁱⁱⁱ Therefore, this specific genre of literature is commonly referred to as Vaishnava literature. The spread of Vaishnavism allowed Odia women to showcase their talents, which had previously been suppressed publicly. The Odia women were encouraged to abandon *Puradaha*, engage in open discussions, and present their works.^{iv}

Madhavi Dasi

Madhavi Dasi's birthplace is Bentapura, a Bramhagiri village within the Puri district. Madhavi Dasi was widowed at a young age. Her brother Sikhi Mohanti was a disciple of Sri Chaitanya Deva. Due to her gender, she could not become a direct disciple of Chaitanya Deva, as he strictly adhered to the principles of Sanyasa and refrained from interacting with women. Therefore, Madhavi Dasi was acknowledged as a half-disciple. Chaitanya Deva had four disciples: Ray Ramanand, Rupa Goswami, Sikhi Mohanty (who happened to be the brother of Madhavi Dasi), and Madhavi Dasi herself. Under the guidance of her uncle Bhavananda Roy, she embarked on a scholarly exploration of diverse literature encompassing religion, philosophy, Purana, and Vaishnava literature. Following that, she engaged in the creation of Vaisnava literature. Madhavi Dasi's compositions exclusively utilise the language known as *Brajaboli* or *Brajabhasha*. The dialect known as *Brajabhasha* originated in Sri Brundaban and is primarily associated with the Vaishnavas. The script used in Bengali, Brajabhasa, exhibits notable similarities to the Odia language.

Brundavati Dasi

Brundabati Dasi's place of birth is the village of Malipada, located in the district of Puri. Brundabati married Chandra Sekhara Mohapatra, a karana in caste. Chandra Sekhara's family has been devout followers of the *Brajavaisnava* School for multiple generations. Chandra Sekhara's family chose to use the title Rasa instead of Mohapatra. With the encouragement of her husband's family, she composed *Kavya Purnatama Chandrodaya* during the reign of Dibyasingha Deva of Khurda in the late 17th century AD. Her husband Chandrasekhara had already composed the *Kavya* titled *Srikrishnachandra tatva*. Her son Bhima Dasa had written *Bhaktiratnavali*, and her grandson authored *Upasana-chandrodava*.^v

Nisanka Raya Rani

Nisanka Raya Rani was born in 1788 A.D. in Ganjam. She married Gourchandra Nisanka Ray, the son of Sri Ramachandra Deva, at a very young age. Sri Ramachandra Deva belonged to a small feudal state in that district. Following her marriage, she discovered that her husband was engaging in excessive alcohol consumption and pursuing relationships with other women. Therefore, she redirected her focus toward the pursuit of writing poetry. Following her husband's death, she found herself widowed and decided to return to her father's house. During this time, she wrote *Padmavati Abhilasa* with the support and sponsorship of her father.^{vi}

The Modern Age

Fakir Mohan Senapati, Radha Nath Rai, and Madhusudan Rao appeared during a crucial period in Odia literature. They introduced innovative approaches to establish a logical balance between conventional and modern values.^{vii} They had a strong enthusiasm for creating schools for females because of the insufficient availability of educational institutions for girls and the limited access to female education. Their Literary compositions began to reflect the values associated with the consciousness of nationalism.^{viii} Fakir Mohan's *Revati* illustrates women's education and emancipation within that age's societal and social framework. In the subsequent century, traditional women rose to significant positions in teaching and writing. Kokila Devi, Kuntalakumari Sabat, Sita Devi Khadanga, Sarala Devi, Vasant Kumari Patnaik, and Ayatprabha Devi pioneered patriarchal disruption.

The enrollment statistics of female students across various educational institutions spanning from 1874 to 1875.^{ix}

District	Christian	Hindu	Musalman	Total
Cuttack	399	30	4	433
Puri	92			92
Balesore	111	177	21	309
Total	602	207	25	834

Sulakshana Devi:

Sulakshana Devi was born in 1829 A.D. in the feudal state of Tigiria and married Sri Nityananda Patnaik of Dhenkanal at the age of fourteen. Her son Damodar Patnaik was designated the Dewan of Dhenkanal and reputed

to be a ‘Ustad’ in the realm of Odissi songs. The son’s performances of musical ragas had a cumulative impact on his mother’s poetic contemplations. She was strongly inclined toward religious beliefs and practices from an early age. After losing her husband at fifty, she wholeheartedly pursued divine service. To articulate her spiritual musings, she authored a literary work entitled *Parijatmala*. The collection of poems exhibits a profusion of Bhakti sentiment.^x

Suchitra Devi:

Suchitra Devi, born in 1881 A.D., belonged to a prominent Karan family. She married Raghabananda Das from the village Kurunjipur in the Puri district. Despite being employed in the Government administrative service, her husband actively contributed articles to various literary journals. The collection of traditional stories from Odisha was compiled and published by her with the guidance of her husband. However, her primary focus lies in the realm of poetry. The poetic composition titled ‘Kavitalahari’ was published in 1901 AD. Following that, six additional editions of this book were published. This statement highlights the widespread appeal and recognition of her design. Devahuti Dei, the eldest daughter, has significantly contributed to Odia literature as a writer.^{xi}

Annapurna Devi:

Annapurna Devi was born into a Karan family in the year 1883 A.D. in the Ganjam region. Her father’s name was Govinda Patnaik, and her mother was Subhadra. Annapurna received her education in Pathsala, which was popular during that time. Her education was completed by the age of nine. Upon finishing her education, she studied various religious texts such as *Odia Bhagavata*, *Ramayana*, *Mahabharata*, and *Chaitanya Charitamurta*. Annapurna married Sri Ramachandra Patnaik of Purusottampur in the district of Ganjam in 1900 A.D. when she was seventeen. Sri Ramachandra Patnaik held a position as a low-paid employee within the court of the feudal king of Parlakhimundi. Annapurna’s poetic talent flourished with her husband’s support and sponsorship. She edited the magazine *Sahakara*, which Sri Lakshminarayana initially founded. She composed *Kavya’s Padyamala*, which was edited and published in 1904 A.D. by Pandit Nilamani Vidyaratna. The text mentions several components: *Prarthana*, *Go-dhana*, *Bahuda*, *Puspa*, *Patipatninka Prathama*, *Bidhatare Prathama*,

and *Jibe Daya*. In 1905, Part II of *Padyamala* was printed and published. In her second edition, compositions like *Bramhaprarthana*, *Nishihelani*, *Brukshamanankara shove*, *Bhaktiprarthana*, and *Sansara Chitra* were very famous.^{xii}

Shailabala Das

The daughters of Sri Viswanath Kar, the founder of the Bramha Samaj of Odisha, Prativa, Suprava, and Shailabala (adopted daughter of Utkala Gourab Madhusdan Das), were well-educated. Shailabala Das, the adopted daughter of eminent barrister Madhusudan Das, sailed to England in 1918 A.D. to learn advanced methods of education. While in England, she wrote a diary called *Bilat Prabasa*, which was regularly published in *Utkala Sahitya*. After returning to Cuttack and permanently living there, she started considering the idea of founding a Girls' School dedicated to girls' education. Before, there was already a girls' school in operation with a curriculum that extended up to the middle vernacular level. The language of instruction was both Bengali and Odia. Basanti, the daughter of Bhaktakavi Madhusudan Rao, and Nishamani, the daughter of Raibahadur Nandakishore Ray, became the first female candidate to pass the Middle School scholarship examination in 1886 A.D. After a period of one to two years, both Reba (Reba Ray) and Basumati, who is the daughter of the renowned lawyer Priyanath Chatterjee, completed the same exams. Avanti, another daughter of Madhusudan Rao, graduated from this School in 1892.^{xiii}

Reba Ray:

Ms Reba Ray founded a school for girls in Cuttack called Model Girls' School. Smt. Ray exerted much effort to enhance this institution through physical labour and financial expenditure. Chandramukhi Sarangi successfully cleared the entrance examination at this educational institution. She had converted to Christianity. Ms Ray recruited Brahma and female teachers to instruct at this school. Ms. Shailabala Das, in partnership with Ms. Reba Ray, transformed this Model Girls' School into Ravenshaw Girls' School. This marked the initial and enduring progress in the promotion of women's education in Odisha. Subsequently, the Government of Odisha assumed control of this private school and subsequently incorporated Intermediate classes in Arts. In 1904 A.D., she published a compilation called *Anjali*, which had forty poems. In addition, she revised a document

entitled ‘Prabhat’. Sakuntala, a short story authored by Reba Ray, is widely recognised as the inaugural original short story penned by a female writer in the Oriya language.^{xiv}

Kuntalakumari Sabat:

Kuntalakumari Sabat was the first Odia lady to serve as a lady doctor. Alongside her career as a lady doctor, she also pursued her literary pursuits and established herself as a worthy writer in Odia literature. Kuntalakumari Sabat was born in a Christian family in 1900 A.D. and died in 1938 A. D. at the early age of thirty-eight. She spent her childhood and teens in Burma due to her father, Daniel Sabat, who was employed there. After returning from Burma, she joined the Medical School and surprised her lecturers and classmates by topping every exam. After converting to Hinduism through Arya Samaj, she married Krishnaprasad Bramhachari in Delhi. After marriage, she moved to Delhi. She died unexpectedly when her medical and literary careers were at their peak. The main pieces of his repertoire include *Sphulinga*, *Anjali*, *Ahwana*, *Archana*, and *Prema Chintamani*. Set against a romantic backdrop, her poems elevated the imagination to its highest extent.^{xv}

Rama Devi

Rama Devi, often known as ‘Belu’ among her family, was born in Cuttack on 3rd December 1899. Her father’s name was Gopalballav Das, and her mother’s name was Basanta Kumari Devi. Her grandfather was Madhusudan Das, the pride of Utkal. In childhood, she heard her mother’s stories of Ramayana and Mahabharata. In 1914, she married Gopabandhu Choudhury, who left the government service and joined the National Congress. After listening to the speech of Mahatma Gandhi on the river bank of Kathajoori in 1921, she donated all her ornaments to the Tilak Swaraj Fund. She accompanied her husband to the Alakashram at Jagatsinghpur and subsequently to Bari.^{xvi} She worked actively for the freedom struggle and participated in the Bhoodan Movement in Odisha. In 1962, she devoted herself to serving the wounded soldiers in Assam. The Utkal University offered her a Doctorate for her service. The Jamunala Bajaj Foundation also rewarded her. To preserve her memory, the Rama Devi College was established at Bhubaneswar, which later assumed the status of a university. She possessed strong writing skills. The autobiography *Jeevan Pathe* by Rama Devi is considered a timeless masterpiece. Her active participation in the freedom movement, the

Bhoodan Movement, and efforts to combat untouchability have rightfully positioned her as a prominent figure among the female freedom fighters in contemporary Odisha. She breathed her last on 22 July 1985.^{xvii}

Sarala Devi:

Sarala Devi was born in an affluent Karana family at Balikuda of the Cuttack district on 9th August 1904 A.D. Her father was Basudev Kanungo, and her mother was Padmavati Devi. Her family was associated with the family of Madhusudan Das, the Pride of Utkal. Her uncle was the Deputy Collector of Banki. She was educated there. After M.E. School, she married Bhagirathi Mohapatra of Jagatsinghpur. Inspired by her husband, she joined the freedom struggle. She actively participated in the non-cooperation, Civil Disobedience and Quit India Movement. She held the position of president in the Utkal Sahitya Samaj, which is the foremost literary organisation in Odisha. She submitted her essays to *Asha*, *Nabina*, *Nababharati*, Utkal Sahitya, and other publications that focused on women's issues. She breathed her last on four October 1986.^{xviii}

Sarala Devi was the first woman in Orissa to:^{xix}

1. Gave a speech at the INC session in Karachi.
2. Represented in Nehru's Planning Commission.
3. Member of Utkal University's Senate Board.
4. Participated in Dr. Radhakrishnan's educational committee.
5. Jailed for defying salt law in Orissa.
6. Joined All-India Congress Committee.
7. Elected twice to the All-India Women's Conference standing committee.
8. Received two awards from Orissa Sahitya Academy.
9. Female legislator in Orissa Legislative Assembly.
10. Temporarily served as speaker of the Orissa Legislative Assembly.
11. Director of Indian Women's Bank.
12. Vice President at Utkal Sahitya Samaj.
13. President of Women's Development Cooperative Society.

Malati Devi:

On 26 July 1904, Malati Devi was born into a noble family in Calcutta. Her father was Kumudnath Sen, an advocate by profession, and her mother, Snehalata Devi. Her childhood name was Minu; later, she became famous

as Nu-Ma. She passed Matriculation in the first division, and when Naba Krushna Choudhury went to read at Shantiniketan, she fell in love with him and married him. Returning to Odisha, Malati Devi actively participated in the freedom struggle. She endeavoured to elevate the peasants and actively engaged in the Civil Disobedience Movement and Quit India Movement. She also greatly propelled the Prajamandal movement. She was also a poetess. She achieved the highest position as a Sarvodayee in Odisha. She passed away in 1998 at the Baji Rout hostel in Angul.^{xx}

Aparna Devi

Aparna Devi was a well-known female author and a freedom fighter. She wrote *Utkalbharati Kuntalakumari*, *Kabita-kalpalata*, *Indumati*. Though less educated or accomplished than Kuntalakumari Sabat, she was a great writer. Her *Indumati Kavya* is famous in Odia literature. In this poem, she describes a woman's heartfelt sentiments in simple language. Unfortunately, when Aparna Devi emerged as a writer, poets and writers such as Fakirmohan, Madhusudan, and Radhanath no longer existed. The Satyabadi group, which led Oriya literature since 1910 A.D., were imprisoned. For Odisha's political and national consciousness, Rama Devi, Malati Chowdhury, Sarala Devi, and others broke the 'purdah' tradition and sacrificed themselves for freedom.^{xxi}

Harapriya Devi

Harapriya Devi is the cousin sister of Sarala Devi and Nirmala Devi. Her literary works are based on the issues the country and the nation faced then. Through her poetry, she paints a panoramic picture of life in the country and the feeling of devotion. Compositions such as *Hemantalakshmi*, *Chaitrasandhya*, *Phagunarane*, *Saratpalle*, and *Aryanari O Rastradvaja*, amongst others, fall under this category.^{xxii}

Bidyutprava Devi

Bidyutprave Devi compiled and published an enormous collection of poems. She was recognised as an established writer in the literary world. Her collection of poems is organised into eleven sections: (1) *Lokayana*, (2) *Pallipathe*, (3) *Sundara a dhara*, (4) *Priya O Priya*, (5) *Gatha*, (6) *Sradhanjali*, (7) *Khadyotika*, (8) *Bhaktimalva*, (9) *Gadya kavita*, (10) *Jahaku-jive*, and (11) *Kaanla jibana*.^{xxiii}

Women were imprisoned for their involvement in the freedom movement against colonial rule.^{xxiv}

Sl. No	Name	Place	Year of Imprisonment
1	Sarala Devi	Cuttack	1930
2	Malati Devi	Cuttack	1930, 1932, 1942
3	Rama Devi	Cuttack	1930, 1932, 1942
4	Radhamani Devi	Puri	1932
5	Subhadra Devi	Balesore	1932
6	Janhavi Devi	Balesore	1932
7	Harapriya Devi	Cuttack	1932, 1942
8	Priyambada Devi	Cuttack	1932, 1940, 1942
9	Sunamani Devi	Puri	1932, 1942
10	Krushnakamini Devi	Cuttack	1932
11	Sobhabati Devi	Ganjam	1932, 1942
12	Ashalata Acharya	Cuttack	1932
13	Bimala Dutt	Cuttack	1932
14	Arnapurna Rath	Ganjam	1932
15	Gunamanjari Devi	Puri	1932
16	Sundaramani Devi	Puri	1932
17	Saraswati Devi	Cuttack	1932
18	Nirupama Devi	Sachidananda Jena	1932
19	Kshetramani Devi	Balesore	1932
20	Ambika Devi	Balesore	1932
21	Kumuduni Devi	Balesore	1932
22	Kokila Devi	Balesore	1932
23	Tulasi Devi	Balesore	1932
24	Kousalya Devi	Balesore	1932
25	Kumari Adhramani Devi	Balesore	1932
26	Sushila Devi	Cuttack	1932
27	Karuna Choudhari	Cuttack	1932
28	Kumari Arnapurna Choudhuri	Cuttack	1932, 1942
29	Mohini Devi	Ahiyas	1932
30	Kumari Chhaya Devi	Ahiyas	1932
31	Kumuda Devi	Rampa, Cuttack	1932

32	Malati Devi	Neula	1932
33	Malati Devi	Kalyanpur	1932
34	Hiramani Devi	Rampa, Cuttack	1932
35	Sushila Ghosh	Kabirpur, Cuttack	1932
36	Suka Devi	Balesore	1932
37	Sakhi Devi	Balesore	1932
38	Ahalya Devi	Balesore	1932
39	Kusuma Kumari Devi	Kalyanpur	1932
40	Kumari Nishamani Devi	Bhubaneswar, Cuttack	1932
41	Hemalata Devi	Ganjam	1932
42	Manika Devi	Alobhala, Cuttack	1932
43	Jumpei Dei	Cuttack	1932
44	Hiramani Behera	Cuttack	1932
45	Kandhamala Devi	Kandhamala	1932
46	Charubala Devi	Cuttack	1932
47	Kiranabala Sen	Dhaka	1932
48	Mangala Sen	Dhaka	1932
49	Kumari Godabari Devi	Cuttack	1942
50	Kumari Karana Lekha Ray	Cuttack	1942
51	Kumari Uttara Choudhury	Cuttack	1942
52	Kumari Sankuntala Devi	Cuttack	1942
53	Sashibala Kanungo	Cuttack	1942
54	Hiramani Kanungo	Cuttack	1942
55	Bela Dei	Cuttack	1942
56	Nishamani Devi	Ganeswarpur, Cuttack	1942
57	Bilashi Devi	Ganeswarpur, Cuttack	1942
58	Kshetramani Devi	Tentulipada, Cuttack	1942
59	Usha Devi	Rampa, Cuttack	1942
60	Kumari Parbati Giri	Sambalpur	1942
61	Prabhabati Devi	Sambalpur	1942
62	Jambubati Devi	Sambalpur	1932
63	Nilamani Devi	Puri	1932
64	Jashoda Devi	Balesore	1932

65	Champa Devi	Balesore	1942
66	Bimala Devi	Kaktpur, Puri	1942
67	Kumari Kadambini Devi	Dhaneswar, Cuttack	1932

Conclusion

By opposing the patriarchal society, the women of Odisha elevated women's status and made a crucial contribution to the freedom struggle in India. Examining the manner in which women responded and participated in the independence movement, it is clear that their involvement outside of the National movement contributed to power and energy. The surge of empathy and recognition among the general populace highlighted the benefits of women's participation. This motivated male comrades to make the Movement more intense and vigorous. The women of Odisha, through their sacrifice, diligent efforts, and assistance to their male counterparts, motivated the ordinary people to actively engage in India's fight for independence. The Gandhian programs were successfully implemented in Odisha. The participation of Odia women in the freedom struggle of India in Odisha was highly successful.

End Note

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